

The “Event Horizon concept” dataset gathering and authoring system

The Authors here describe the “Event Horizon concept” as a shared multi-contributor knowledge database devoted to authoritatively accumulate info(s) on whatever occurred event by a .app-like multimedia interface also running on an individual smart device.

The system supports the operator(s) *Lifelong learning* and *Experiential Learning* by structuring and sharing with the expert(s) via IT & IoT the data that the operator gathers time by time or event by event.

The expert(s) Authors validate the data and retribute to the operator(s) their authoritative opinion(s) on the event(s) or the shared data. Experts may also support the operator by suggesting approaches to dataset collection or event(s) scrutiny.

The System works as a free mutual data & services sharing between 1) the operator(s) that submit the data they gather to the expert(s) Authors and 2) the Authors that retribute their interpretation(s) to the operator(s).

So that the data remain available for Authors and the interpretations for the operators, consider the economical use of the concept in case of agreement among the actors of the interaction, i.e. one/several expert(s) one/several user(s) for the use of a subset of the System accumulated dataset.

